

1 **INDUCED LACTATION IN DAIRY GOATS**

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5 Virgin goats were hormonally treated to induce lactation, with or without the use of a
6 prolactin releasing agent (reserpine). Udders grew rapidly after treatment and milking started
7 in all goats 21 d later. Reserpine treated goats produced 25% more milk than control goats but
8 milk yield was only 55% of primiparous goats after kidding. Milk composition was normal
9 from d 3 of induced lactation onwards. Goats were mated on d 120, but only 21% of the goats
10 became pregnant. Lactation induction was effective in virgin goats but was unpractical
11 because of low milk yield and reduced fertility.

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INDUCED LACTATION IN DAIRY GOATS

**Mammogenesis and Induced Lactation with or without Reserpine in
Nulliparous Dairy Goats**

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ABSTRACT

Fourteen nulliparous goats were used to evaluate the effects of a standard protocol for inducing lactation with or without using a prolactin releasing agent (reserpine). Goats were estrus synchronized and submitted to a hormonal challenge consisting of daily s.c. injections of estradiol-17 β and progesterone (0.5 and 1.25 mg/kg BW, respectively) for 7 d (d 1 to 7). Goats were divided into 2 groups and i.m. injected with 1 mg/d of reserpine (n = 7) or vehicle as control (n = 7) on d 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20. Lactation was triggered by i.m. injections of dexamethasone (10 mg/d) during d 18 to 20. Goats were machine-milked once daily from d 21 to 120 at which goats were mated jointly with herdmates after the buck effect. Milk was measured and sampled daily during wk 1 of lactation and weekly thereafter. Udder traits were measured in all goats at d -2 (before the induction treatment), and d 35 and 100 (during lactation). Goats initiated lactation on d 21 (100%) and milk yield increased logarithmically ($R^2 = 0.95$) thereafter. Difference in milk yield between control and reserpine goats increased as lactation advanced, peaking at wk 10 of lactation at which reserpine goats yielded greater milk than control goats (1,079 vs. 850 mL/d, respectively). However, milk yield at the peak averaged only 55% of peak milk yield observed in primiparous goats from the same herd. Composition of initial milk (d 21) was lower than the expected for colostrums. Milk composition steadied after d 3 of lactation. No differences between goat groups were detected for milk fat, protein, casein, or whey protein, but milk of control goats contained greater non protein nitrogen than reserpine goats. Teat length increased in control goats during mammogenesis (d -2 to 35) but steadied in reserpine goats. Distance between teats, and volume and depth of the udder increased similarly in both goat groups during mammogenesis and lactation. After mating, 82% of herdmates became pregnant, whereas only 21% of the experimental goats conceived (1 reserpine and 2 control goats), revealing the occurrence of side effects after the lactation induction treatment. In conclusion, lactation induction was

50 effective and reserpine improved milk yield in nulliparous goats, but it seems that neither the
51 obtained milk yield nor the side effects on fertility support its recommendation in practice.

52 **Key Words:** lactation induction, prolactin, milk composition, dairy goat

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INTRODUCTION

55 Smith and Schanbacher (1973) proposed a protocol in which lactation was induced in dairy
56 cows by a 7-d estradiol and progesterone treatment. Compared to what occurs during
57 pregnancy, mammary growth during lactation induction is considered insufficient and varies
58 widely between animals. Therefore, induced lactation has variable success rate (58 to 80%)
59 and milk yield (50 to 106% of natural lactation) in cows (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973;
60 Collier et al., 1975) and ewes (Head et al., 1980). Researchers tried to improve the
61 consistency of response of induced cows and ewes by the inclusion of corticoids (Chakriyarat
62 et al., 1978; Head et al., 1980), reserpine (Collier et al., 1977; Kensinger et al., 1979),
63 placental lactogen (Byatt et al., 1997), somatotropin (Kann, 1997), or prostaglandin (Lukas et
64 al., 2003).

65 Induced lactation has received little attention in dairy goats compared to dairy cows and
66 ewes. First attempts to induce lactation in dairy goats (Cowie et al., 1965; Hart and Morant,
67 1980) used long time steroid priming (35 to 140 d), which is unpractical and may be
68 uneconomic. Fowler et al. (1991) used estrogen and progesterone for 11 d, followed by
69 dexamethasone for 3 d and reserpine during the last 5 d. The experiment of Fowler et al.
70 (1991) had no control goats that had not been treated with reserpine. Chilliard et al. (1986)
71 used the Smith and Schanbacher (1973) 7-d treatment for lactation induction in dairy goats
72 which yielded 55% of milk produced by natural lactating goats. As far as we know, no studies
73 are available comparing the effects of improved protocols of induced lactation in dairy goats.

74 Hart and Morant (1980) concluded that increased levels of plasma prolactin (**PRL**) are
75 essential for a successful induction of mammary growth and lactation in dairy goats. No
76 increase in udder size was observed when PRL was maintained at basal concentrations by
77 injecting bromocriptine, a PRL-inhibitor. Moreover, increasing the dose of estrogens and
78 decreasing that of progesterone led to an increase in both plasma PRL and udder size and
79 stimulated the onset of lactation.

80 In the present study we included reserpine, a PRL release agent, in the induction protocol.
81 Reserpine blocks the inhibitory effects of dopamine on the pituitary cells that secrete PRL
82 (lactotrophs) by binding to dopamine receptors. Collier et al. (1977) and Kensinger et al.
83 (1979) injected reserpine from d 2 to 14 or 16 of the treatment in dairy cows. The PRL levels
84 are low during the 7-d steroids injection because of the inhibitory effect of progesterone on
85 PRL secretion, increase from d 14 to 17 of treatment, and then decrease (Erb et al., 1976;
86 Kann, 1997). However, levels of PRL during pregnancy are high for a few days before
87 kidding (Davis et al., 1979). Therefore, we hypothesized that it may be convenient to extend
88 the injections of reserpine until d 20 of treatment (1 d before milking) to simulate better the
89 natural hormonal milieu at kidding.

90 The objective of this study was to evaluate milk yield, milk composition, and udder
91 morphology changes in nulliparous dairy goats induced to lactate with or without reserpine
92 treatment.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

95 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
96 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
97 Barcelona.

98

99 *Animals, Treatments, and Management Conditions*

100 A total of 14 nulliparous Murciano-Granadina goats (17.3 ± 0.1 mo of age and 37.5 ± 1.0
101 kg BW) from the herd of the SIGCE (Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals) of the
102 Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona were allocated in 2 balanced experimental groups. To
103 eliminate the possible effect of the reproductive state on the response to hormones used to
104 induce lactation, estrus was synchronized (February 1st) using 40 mg fluoroprogesterone
105 vaginal sponges (Chronolone, Intervet, Salamanca, Spain) for 14 d prior to the initiation of
106 the lactation induction scheme. Pregnant mare serum gonadotrophin (300 IU; Intervet) was
107 i.m. injected at the time of sponges withdrawal.

108 Induction of lactation started 7 d after sponges withdrawal and all goats received daily s.c.
109 injections of estradiol-17 β (0.5 mg/kg BW) and progesterone (1.25 mg/kg BW) in 2 portions
110 at 0800 h and 1800 h on d 1 to 7. Goats were i.m. injected with 1 mg/d reserpine (**RES**; n = 7)
111 or vehicle as controls (**CON**; n = 7) at 0900 h on d 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20. Eight goats came
112 from 4 sets of twins and were assigned to CON and RES groups, balanced according to BW
113 and milk yield of mothers. Lactation in all goats was triggered by dexamethasone (10 mg/d)
114 injected s.c. at 0900 h on d 18 to 20 and machine milking was initiated on d 21 and lasted for
115 14 wk (d 21 to 120). Goats were checked twice daily (after milking and when goats returned
116 from the pasture) for 7 wk for estrus behavior signs (tail wagging, mounting, vulval swelling
117 and redness, vaginal mucous discharge, and bleating) caused by the hormonal treatment.

118 Hormones and reserpine were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich Química,
119 Barcelona, Spain). Estradiol-17 β , progesterone, and dexamethasone were dissolved in
120 absolute ethanol to give concentrations of 20, 50, and 10 g/L, respectively. Solutions were
121 protected from light and stored at room temperature (estradiol and progesterone) or at 4°C
122 (dexamethasone). Reserpine solution was prepared just before injection by dissolving 10 mg

123 reserpine in 0.5 mL glacial acetic acid and brought to a volume of 10 mL by sterilized
124 distilled water.

125 Goats grazed for 6 h daily and were fed indoors with dehydrated ryegrass hay ad libitum
126 (12% CP; as fed), 0.6 kg commercial concentrate (6.4 MJ NE_L/kg and 16% CP; as fed), and
127 0.5 kg alfalfa pellets (17% CP; as fed). Goats were milked once daily at 0900 h in a double-12
128 stall parallel milking parlor (Westfalia-Separator Ibérica, Granollers, Spain) with recording
129 jars (2 L ± 5%) and a low milk pipeline. Milking machine was set at a vacuum pressure of 42
130 kPa, a pulsation rate of 90 pulses/min, and a pulsation ratio of 66%. Milking routine included
131 machine milking, stripping before cluster removal, and teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-
132 cide plus, Henkel Hygiene, Barcelona, Spain).

133 Experimental nulliparous goats were mated in May jointly with their herdmates when all of
134 them were still lactating and milked once daily. Mating started after natural estrus induction
135 by the buck effect using a teaser buck for 4 d, which was then replaced by fertile bucks (1
136 buck per 20 goats). The mating period lasted for 70 d.

137

138 ***Sample Collection, Analyses, and Measurements***

139 Milk yield was recorded daily during the first 3 wk of lactation and thereafter on 2
140 consecutive days weekly until wk 14 of lactation. Milk composition was evaluated daily
141 during the wk 1, weekly from wk 2 to 8, and biweekly from wk 10 to 14. A milk sample of
142 approximately 100 mL was collected and preserved with an anti-microbial tablet (Bronopol,
143 Broad Spectrum Micro-tabs II, D&F Control Systems Inc., San Ramon, CA) at 4°C.

144 Unhomogenized milk samples were analyzed with a near infrared spectrometer (FOSS
145 NIRSystems 5000, Hillerød, Denmark) for content of TS, fat, protein (N × 6.38), true protein
146 and CN (Albanell et al., 2003). Whey protein was calculated by the difference between true
147 protein and CN, and NPN was calculated by the difference between protein and true protein.

148 Udder morphology traits were measured 2 d before the hormonal treatment, and 7 h after
149 milking, at wk 2 and 12 of induced lactation (d 35 and 105, respectively) as described by
150 Peris et al. (1999). Measured udder traits were: teat length (mm) from teat base until teat
151 orifice, distance between teats (cm) as the distance between the 2 teat orifices, udder depth
152 (cm) as the distance between rear udder attachment and udder base, and udder volume (mL)
153 measured in a bucket by water displacement.

154

155 *Statistical Analyses*

156 Data were analyzed by the PROC MIXED for repeated measurements of SAS (SAS 9.1;
157 SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). The statistical mixed model contained the random effect of the
158 animal within the treatment (reserpine vs. control); the fixed effects of treatment and week of
159 lactation; the interaction between treatment and week of lactation; and the residual error.
160 Random effect of udder half nested within animal was added to the model in the analysis of
161 teat length trait. Data of total milk yield during the experiment were analyzed by one way
162 ANOVA using PROC GLM with a model containing the effect of the treatment and the
163 residual error. Pearson's correlation coefficients between udder morphology traits were also
164 calculated.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

167 Doses of estradiol and progesterone used in the present study agreed with those previously
168 used in goats (Chilliard et al., 1986) and ewes (Head et al., 1980; Kann, 1997), but were 5
169 times greater than those used in dairy cows (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973; Collier et al.,
170 1977; Kensinger et al., 1979). Greater hormonal doses might be necessary in ewes and goats
171 because these animals have greater concentrations of estradiol and progesterone during
172 pregnancy than cows (Convey, 1974), especially if they bear multiple fetuses (Manalu et al.,

173 1996). However, the ratio between estradiol and progesterone (1 : 2.5) in our study was the
174 same ratio used in ewes and cows.

175 Udders of 7 goats began to fill with mammary secretion at d 14 of treatment (1 wk before
176 the beginning of milking). No estrus behavior signs were observed during the 7-d injection
177 period of estradiol and progesterone, but estrus was observed in 2 goats at d 12 of treatment
178 (14%) and gradually increased until d 17 when 12 goats (86%) had estrus signs. Most goats
179 had estrus signs until d 7 of lactation (d 28 of treatment) and some goats continued with estrus
180 until d 15 of lactation. A similar estrus behavior with time after treatment was also reported in
181 dairy cows (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973), although hormonal doses used in our goats were
182 greater.

183 With regard to reserpine injections, 2 of the 7 goats treated with RES showed slight
184 shivering and drowsiness after the third injection. Reserpine acts by blocking the
185 intraneuronal storage of neurotransmitters (dopamine, serotonin, and norepinephrine), both
186 centrally and peripherally, and has a known β -adrenergic effect on the cerebral circulation of
187 the goat diminishing the vasoconstriction induced by nerve stimulation (Lluch et al., 1975).
188 However, by 48 h after RES injection these side effects to RES were not observed.

189

190 ***Milk Yield***

191 Data of milk yield for induced lactation are shown in Figure 1. Milk yield obtained at the
192 first milking (d 21) was similar between CON and RES goats (600 ± 94 vs. 725 ± 87 mL; $P =$
193 0.347). Similarly, daily milk yield did not vary ($P = 0.253$) between CON (659 ± 81 mL/d)
194 and RES (793 ± 75 mL/d) goats from wk 1 to 7 of lactation (d 21 to 70). However, the
195 difference between groups increased as lactation advanced, and from wk 8 to 14 (77 to 120 d)
196 RES goats ($1,052 \pm 94$ mL/d) produced 28% greater milk ($P < 0.10$) than CON goats ($825 \pm$
197 100 mL/d). Week 8 of induced lactation (d 77) was in April when daylight length was

198 increasing rapidly. Increased milk yield of dairy goats with longer days has been reported
199 before (Salama et al., 2005) and may be due to elevated secretion of PRL. Forsyth and Lee
200 (1993) reported that goats treated with bromocriptine at parturition were unable to show the
201 normal seasonal rise of PRL in summer, probably because of limited lactotrophs in the
202 pituitary of bromocriptine-treated goats. As RES goats should have had greater levels of PRL
203 than CON goats before the initiation of lactation, we speculate that RES goats had more
204 lactotrophs and responded better to increased daylight length than CON goats.

205 Peak milk yield in both groups was at wk 10 of lactation (d 90) and differed ($P = 0.084$)
206 between CON (850 mL/d) and RES (1,079 mL/d) goats. Goats from the same breed and herd
207 peaked earlier at wk 3 to 4 after kidding (Salama et al., 2003). The delayed peak during
208 induced lactation could be partially due to continued mammary proliferation after the start of
209 lactation, as supported by the increase in udder volume during lactation (see later). Similarly,
210 peak milk yield during induced lactation was at wk 9 to 11 in dairy cows (Collier et al., 1975;
211 Kensinger et al., 1979), wk 7 in ewes (Head et al., 1980) and wk 9 in dairy goats (Fowler et
212 al., 1991). Fowler et al. (1991) reported that most udder development in goats induced to
213 lactate took place after the cessation of steroid treatment, achieving a maximum at wk 8 of the
214 induced lactation.

215 Using milk yield at peak ≥ 0.5 L/d as an arbitrary criterion of lactation induction success,
216 100% of goats were successfully induced to lactate. When this criterion was increased to ≥ 1
217 L /d, success rate was 29 and 71% in CON and RES goats, respectively. Collier et al. (1977)
218 reported that success rate, defined as achieving peak milk yield ≥ 9 kg/d, was 55 and 100% in
219 control and reserpine-treated cows, respectively. For all groups, correlations between milk
220 yield at wk 1 and both milk yield at peak ($r = 0.87$) and lactation success rate defined as peak
221 milk yield ≥ 1 L/d ($r = 0.84$) were significant ($P < 0.001$).

222 Peak milk yield values in CON and RES goats were 49 and 60% of peak milk yield values
223 obtained after kidding in primiparous goats milked once daily from the same breed and herd
224 (Salama et al., 2003). Similarly, multiparous goats induced into lactation by Chilliard et al.
225 (1986) produced 55% of the milk during natural lactations. Moreover, milk yield of dairy
226 cows induced into lactation averaged 50 to 90 % of milk obtained after parturition (Smith and
227 Schanbacher, 1973; Chakriyarat et al., 1978).

228 Throughout the 14 wk lactation period (d 21 to 120), RES goats (922 ± 85 mL/d) produced
229 24% greater daily milk yield than CON goats (742 ± 92 mL/d), but this difference was not
230 significant ($P = 0.178$) probably as a consequence of the high variability commonly observed
231 between animals in their response to the hormonal treatment. Total milk yield in 100 d of
232 milking was 73 ± 9 and 91 ± 9 L in CON and RES goats, respectively ($P = 0.202$). Similarly,
233 dairy cows injected with reserpine on d 8, 10, 12, and 14 or on d 13 to 16 of treatment
234 produced greater milk yield and showed a greater peak milk yield than control cows (Collier
235 et al., 1977).

236

237 ***Milk Composition***

238 Milk composition on the first day of lactation was similar between CON and RES goats
239 (Figure 2) and averaged: TS; 17.0%, fat; 5.66%, protein; 6.61%, CN; 3.96%, whey protein;
240 2.62%, and NPN; 0.33%. In the present study whey protein, most of which is Ig, was low in
241 the first day milk and only represented 40% of total milk protein. Caja et al. (2006) reported
242 that whey protein accounts for 72% of total protein in the normal colostrum of dairy goats
243 from the same breed and under similar exploitation conditions.

244 Smith et al. (1971) obtained a fluid nearly identical to colostrum on d 17 of treatment and
245 stated that estradiol daily dose in cows should not be lower than 0.1 mg/kg BW for 7 d.

246 Although doses of injected steroids for lactation induction were very high in our study, first

247 milk obtained from goats on d 21 did not fully mimic normal colostrum. Winger et al. (1995)
248 showed that IgG concentration in cow milk peaked on d 15 of treatment and then decreased
249 gradually; and that dexamethasone injection triggered sharp decreases in IgG concentrations
250 in mammary secretions. In agreement with the lactation induction protocol followed, first
251 milking was done on d 21 and dexamethasone was injected from d 18 to 20, which may
252 explain why this milk was different from normal colostrum. Moreover, supposed peak of IgG
253 should have occurred 6 d before, according to Winger et al. (1995), indicating that an earlier
254 first milking would have been preferable.

255 Daily changes in milk composition during wk 1 of lactation are shown in Figure 2. No
256 differences were detected between CON and RES goats on any day except on the second day
257 when milk of CON goats contained greater ($P < 0.05$) fat, CN, and TS. Milk fat, protein, CN
258 and TS percentages in both goat groups were high during the first 2 d of lactation, decreased
259 by d 3 ($P < 0.05$) to standard milk values and remained constant thereafter (Figure 2). Erb et
260 al. (1976) reported high concentrations of progesterone and estrogen in milk until d 4 of
261 induced lactation, and then decreased to normal dairy cow values. Based on results of the
262 current study and Erb et al. (1976), abnormal milk composition and elevated hormone
263 concentration in milk from goats artificially induced into lactation should not be a concern
264 from 3 to 4 d after starting lactation.

265 Throughout the experimental period, milk contents of fat, protein, CN and whey protein
266 were similar between CON and RES goats (Table 1). However, milk TS tended to be greater
267 ($P = 0.158$) in CON than in RES goats, which may be a dilution effect since RES goats tended
268 to produce more milk than CON goats. Milk of CON goats contained greater ($P < 0.05$) NPN
269 than milk of RES goats. If PRL concentration in the blood really differed between the 2
270 groups due to different response to the increased daylight, as previously indicated, differences
271 in milk NPN between groups may be explained. The level of PRL may affect N metabolism

272 in the body, and Brinklow and Forbes (1983) reported increased N retention in sheep when
273 infused with PRL.

274 In our results, CN : Protein ratio was similar between groups and averaged 66%. This value
275 is smaller than normal values reported in milk of dairy goats from the same breed and herd,
276 which ranged between 73 and 76% (Salama et al., 2003).

277

278 ***Udder Morphology***

279 Teat length was small in the virgin goats before treatment, but increased in CON goats from
280 d -2 to 35 (39.7%; $P < 0.05$) due to the hormonal challenge of lactation induction and
281 remained constant thereafter (Table 2). On the contrary, no change in teat length was detected
282 in RES goats from d -2 to 35. Lammers et al. (1999) reported that estrogen implants in
283 prepubertal dairy heifers increased teat length during the treatment period, but the effect was
284 reversed post-treatment which finally reduced teat length by 30%. Effects of estrogen,
285 responsible for ductal growth in the mammary gland, on teat growth were modified in our
286 case by the action of PRL in the RES goats; thus teat growth steadied during mammogenesis
287 and increased during lactation (from d 35 to 105). This effect has not been described
288 previously.

289 Distance between teats increased similarly for CON and RES groups during the
290 experiment, averaging 123% ($P < 0.01$) during mammogenesis and 9% ($P = 0.448$) during
291 lactation (Table 2).

292 We were not able to measure udder volume or udder depth before the hormonal treatment
293 (d -2) because virgin goats had no apparently visible udder. At wk 2 of induced lactation (d
294 35) there were no differences between CON and RES groups for volume and depth of the
295 udder, which averaged 768 mL and 14.2 cm, respectively. Despite milk yield differences ($P =$
296 0.107) between CON (850 mL/d) and RES (1,057 mL/d) goats at wk 12, no differences were

297 detected in udder volume or udder depth. Thus, increased milk yield in RES goats seems to be
298 due to increased mammary cell differentiation rather than to mammary growth.

299 From wk 2 to 12, milk yield in both groups increased by 67%, whereas udder volume
300 increased by only 41% on average. This may indicate that in addition to mammary growth,
301 mammary differentiation is also responsible for increased milk yield during the induced
302 lactation. Fleming et al. (1986) biopsied cows induced into lactation at d 0, 14, and 130 of
303 lactation and found increased mammary differentiation from d 0 to 130. Moreover, Chilliard
304 et al. (1986) reported greater RNA : DNA ratio in mammary glands of goats induced into
305 lactation compared with normal lactating goats at wk 18 of lactation.

306 Milk yield correlated positively with udder volume ($r = 0.605, P < 0.05$; $r = 0.767, P < 0.01$)
307 and udder depth ($r = 0.703, P < 0.01$; $r = 0.751, P < 0.01$) at wk2 and 12, as previously
308 reported in dairy goats during normal lactation (Peris et al., 1999). The distance between teats
309 was not correlated with milk yield at wk2 (d35) or wk 12 (d105). Udder depth and udder
310 volume were correlated at both 2 and 12 wk ($r = 0.718; P < 0.01$). Udder depth was correlated
311 with the distance between teats at 12 wk ($r = 0.557; P < 0.05$). Teat length was not correlated
312 with milk yield or with any other udder morphology traits.

313

314 ***Fertility***

315 Of the 14 experimental goats, only 3 (1 RES and 2 CON goats) became pregnant after
316 mating in May (fertility, 21.4%). The low fertility observed was not attributed to the buck
317 utilized for inseminating the experimental goats because the same buck had also mated 17
318 herdmates; 14 of them kidded (fertility, 82.4%). This result indicates a negative side-effect of
319 the hormonal treatment used on the reproduction of nulliparous goats which was probably
320 related to the high level of estrogens used.

321 The fertility value obtained is much lower than the 56% reported by Collier et al. (1975) in
322 dairy cows after lactation induction. Erb et al. (1976) reported that 88% of cows induced to
323 lactate developed enlarged persistent follicles and treatment with human chorionic
324 gonadotropin was necessary. Persistent follicles might also have been developed in our goats,
325 and although 16 wk elapsed between the last steroid hormone injection and mating, normal
326 estrus cycles have not been resumed. High fertility (93%) was observed (Magliaro et al.,
327 2004) in dairy cows induced to lactate with lower doses of estradiol (0.075 mg/kg BW) than
328 those used by Smith and Schanbacher (1973), although these cows had a history of
329 reproductive problems. This may support the hypothesis that high doses of estradiol, as used
330 in our study, may result in elevated residual estrogen and reduced fertility. Moreover, the high
331 levels of estrogen used may have long term hypothalamic effects.

332

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CONCLUSIONS

334 The 7-d hormonal protocol used was efficient to induce lactation in nulliparous goats and
335 milk yield was improved by using reserpine as a prolactin stimulator. Nevertheless, the
336 obtained milk yield was only one half of that obtained after normal kidding in primiparous
337 goats indicating that induction protocol should be improved for its practical use in goats.
338 Moreover, the reduced fertility observed after the lactation induction treatment suggests the
339 need for a substantial reduction of estrogen doses. In the current state, this technique is not
340 recommended for dairy goat in practice.

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429

430 **Table 1.** Least square means of average milk composition (d 21 to 120) in nulliparous dairy
 431 goats induced to lactate with or without reserpine.

Milk component, %	Control (n = 7)	Reserpine (n = 7)	SED ¹	Effect (<i>P</i> =)
Total solids	13.9	13.6	0.2	0.158
Fat	4.62	4.36	0.24	0.338
Protein	4.29	4.21	0.16	0.639
Casein	2.83	2.74	0.09	0.327
Casein, % of protein	66.4	65.4	1.3	0.462
Whey protein	1.46	1.47	0.08	0.900
Non protein N	0.48	0.41	0.02	0.016

432 ¹ Standard error of the difference.

433

434 **Table 2.** Least square means of udder morphology traits in nulliparous dairy goats induced to
 435 lactate with or without reserpine.

Item	Control (n = 7)	Reserpine (n = 7)	SED ¹	Effect (<i>P</i> =)
Teat length, mm				
Pre-treatment, wk -4	24.7 ^b	24.4 ^b	1.5	0.857
Lactation, wk 2	34.5 ^a	26.0 ^b	3.3	0.017
Lactation, wk 12	33.2 ^a	29.0 ^a	4.2	0.324
Distance between teats, cm				
Pre-treatment, wk -4	6.3 ^c	5.9 ^c	0.7	0.558
Lactation, wk 2	13.5 ^b	13.7 ^b	0.7	0.800
Lactation, wk 12	15.0 ^a	14.6 ^a	0.7	0.622
Udder depth, cm				
Pre-treatment, wk -4	0	0	-	-
Lactation, wk 2	14.1 ^b	14.3 ^b	0.9	0.817
Lactation, wk 12	16.7 ^a	17.1 ^a	0.9	0.648
Udder volume, mL				
Pre-treatment, wk -4	0	0	-	-
Lactation, wk 2	784 ^b	751 ^b	96	0.732
Lactation, wk 12	1,035 ^a	1,119 ^a	96	0.398

436 ^{a,b} Means with different superscript within a column for each parameter differ (*P* < 0.05).

437 ¹ Standard error of the difference.

438

439 **Table 3.** Correlation coefficients among udder traits and milk yield in nulliparous dairy goats
 440 induced to lactate at wk 2 (above diagonal) and wk 12 (below diagonal) of lactation (n = 14).

	Milk yield	Udder volume	Udder depth	Distance between teats	Teat length
Milk yield	-	0.605 [*]	0.703 ^{**}	0.533 [†]	-0.074
Udder volume	0.767 ^{**}	-	0.718 ^{**}	0.193	0.406
Udder depth	0.751 ^{**}	0.718 ^{**}	-	0.322	-0.089
Distance between teats	0.335	0.484 [†]	0.557 [*]	-	-0.030
Teat length	0.064	0.459	0.019	0.074	-

441 [†] $P < 0.10$.

442 ^{*} $P < 0.05$.

443 ^{**} $P < 0.01$.

444

445

446 **Figure 1.** Milk yield of nulliparous dairy goats induced to lactate with (●; n = 7) or without
447 (○; n = 7) reserpine.

448

449

450 **Figure 2.** Milk composition changes during the first week of lactation in nulliparous dairy
 451 goats induced to lactate with (●; n = 7) or without (○; n = 7) reserpine. ^{a, b, c} Means with
 452 different superscript throughout days in control and reserpine goats differ ($P < 0.05$). *
 453 Indicates a difference ($P < 0.05$) between control and reserpine goats.
 454

